

Inhibition effect of imidazoline and hydroypyrimidine derivatives on the corrosion of brass in 0.6 M aqueous sodium chloride solution

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Manuscript received 16 March 2011, accepted 30 May 2011

Abstract : The inhibition effect of *o*-aminobenzoic acid (1), *p*-aminobenzoic acid (2), *o*-benzenesulphonamidobenzoic acid (3), *p*-benzenesulphonamidobenzoic acid (4), 2-(*o*-benzenesulphonamido)phenylimidazoline (5), 2-(*p*-benzenesulphonamido)phenylimidazoline (6), 2-(*o*-benzenesulphonamido)phenyl-1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidine (7) and 2-(*p*-benzenesulphonamido)phenyl-1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidine (8) towards the corrosion of brass in 0.6 M aqueous solution has been studied using potentiodynamic polarization and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy. The corresponding data of 2-(β -benzenesulphonamido)ethylimidazoline (9) and 2-(β -benzenesulphonamido)ethyl-1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidine (10) are included for comparison. It has been observed that introduction of C₆H₅-SO₂ group increases the inhibition efficiency of aminobenzoic acid by 8-12%. When -COOH group is converted to imidazoline or 1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidine group, the inhibition efficiency is further increased by 7-23%. The inhibition efficiency of these compounds increases in the order : 1 < 3 < 2 < 5 < 4 < 6 < 7 < 8. The inhibition efficiency of 8 with 4 × 10⁻⁵ M concentration in the highest which reaches 95.4%. The *para* compounds are better inhibitor than the corresponding *ortho* compounds due to better surface coverage. The hydroypyrimidine derivatives are better inhibitor than the imidazoline derivatives due to more basic character and larger size of the molecules.

Keywords : Derivative, imidazoline, hydroypyrimidine, inhibition effect, brass, corrosion, sodium chloride.

Introduction

Benzimidazole, imidazole, mercaptobenzo-thiazole, benzotriazole and benzoxazole derivatives are corrosion inhibitor for copper and brass¹⁻⁶. Benzimidazole derivatives are also effective inhibitor for iron and steel in HCl solution^{7,8}. Imidazoline derivatives are found to be effective inhibitors for steel against CO₂⁹⁻¹³ and H₂SO₄ corrosion¹⁴. Recently work has been initiated by various workers on the evaluation of corrosion performance of imidazoline derivatives by quantum chemistry and molecular mechanics methods¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Hydroypyrimidine derivatives are synthesized for their antiproliferative activity¹⁸, anti-inflammatory activity¹⁹ and DNA cleavage activity²⁰. These compounds are also potent inhibitors of Interleukin-8-induced neutrophil chemotaxis²¹. Imidazolines and tetrahydropyrimidines are highly basic compounds containing nitrogen donor atom and may function as good corrosion inhibitor for brass. With this aim in view we have chosen *o*-aminobenzoic acid (1) and *p*-aminobenzoic acid as starting materials and prepared *o*-benzenesulphonamidobenzoic acid (3) and *p*-benzenesulphonamidobenzoic acid (4). The carboxylic group is further con-

verted to highly basic imidazoline and tetrahydropyrimidine groups to improve further their inhibition activity and synthesized 2-(*o*-benzenesulphonamido)phenylimidazoline (5), 2-(*p*-benzenesulphonamido)phenylimidazoline (6), 2-(*o*-benzenesulphonamido)phenyl-1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidine (7) and 2-(*p*-benzenesulphonamido)phenyl-1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidine (8). These compounds may act as polydentate chelating agents and expected to be good inhibitors for brass in chloride solution due to the presence of O, N and S atoms, highly basic imidazoline or 1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidine moiety, π electron effect of the benzene ring and a number of adsorption sites. Two electrochemical techniques potentiodynamic polarization and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy have been used to study the effect of the addition of these compounds on the corrosion of brass in 0.6 M aqueous NaCl solution. The corresponding data of 2-(β -benzenesulphonamido)ethylimidazoline (9) and 2-(β -benzenesulphonamido)ethyl-1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidine (10) are included for comparison. The molecular structures of the inhibitors are given in Fig. 1.

Structure of the compounds method	Inhibition Efficiency (%)		
	Tafel Extrapolation method	EIS	Average
	52.7	58.5	55.6
	71.6	75.9	73.8
	64.9	69.5	67.2
	80.1	84.6	82.4
	74.1	79.6	76.9
	87.9	90.1	89.0
	88.1	92.3	90.2
	94.2	96.5	95.4
	65.7	70.5	68.1
	78.3	82.7	80.5

Fig. 1. Molecular structure and inhibition efficiency of the corrosion inhibitors.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

The chemical composition of the commercial brass used in the present study was 59.8% Cu, 40.0% Zn and traces amount of Fe and Pb. The working electrode for potentiodynamic study and EIS measurement was prepared from the brass rod from which only the circular cross section (0.25 cm²) of rod was exposed. The brass sample was polished successively with

(a) belt grinding polishing machine,

(b) metallographic emery paper of increasing fineness of up to 1200 grade and

(c) cloth polishing by Single Disc Polishing Machine CENSICO PMV-T 10-1.

Then the samples were degreased with AR grade ethanol and acetone and rinsed with double distilled water prior to each experiment.

o-Aminobenzoic acid (1) and *p*-aminobenzoic acid (2) were AR grade reagents and used as received or properly purified/prepared following usual procedure. Compounds 3 and 4 were prepared by allowing 1 or 2 (0.1 mol) to react with benzenesulphonyl chloride (0.1 mol) in presence of aqueous Na₂CO₃ solution in warm condition with constant stirring²². Compounds 5 and 6 were prepared by heating a mixture of 3 or 4 and ethylene diamine in 1 : 1 mole ratio at 130–160 °C for 12 h in air atmosphere. The reaction product was cooled, washed with water (pH 8) and the solid obtained was recrystallized from aqueous DMSO. Hydropyridine derivatives (7 and 8) were prepared by using propylene diamine in place of ethylene diamine. IR spectra of these compounds were recorded on Shimadzu spectrophotometer model 8201 PC in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹. NMR data were recorded on Bruker DRX-300 spectrometer. Analytical data of the compounds are given in Tables 1 and 2. The pH measurements were made with an Orion 420A Plus pH meter using 9157BN Triode pH electrode. The pH meter was calibrated with sodium hydrogen phthalate and borax buffer solution in water. For the determination of basic character of the new imidazoline and hydroprymidine derivatives, the following solutions (50 ml) were titrated potentiometrically in water-methanol (1 : 1) at 30 ± 0.5 °C and μ = 0.25 (NaClO₄) against 0.150 M NaOH solution; (a) 0.01 M HClO₄, (b) 0.01 M HClO₄ + 0.02 M 5 H⁺ or

Table 1. Analytical data of the inhibitors

Inhibitors	Percentage yield	Melting points (°C)	Analysis (%) Obsd (Calcd)			pK* values
			C	H	N	
3	70	210	-	-	4.95 (5.05)	-
4	39	203	-	-	5.01 (5.05)	-
5	45	252	59.17 (59.80)	4.70 (4.98)	13.21 (13.95)	8.70
6	35	162	59.40 (59.80)	4.71 (4.98)	13.35 (13.95)	8.60
7	20	230	59.87 (60.95)	5.13 (5.39)	13.10 (13.33)	9.09
8	20	170	59.90 (60.95)	5.35 (5.39)	13.20 (13.33)	9.08
9	46	152	52.10 (52.17)	5.98 (5.92)	16.57 (16.60)	10.51
10	40	148	53.80 (53.93)	6.23 (6.37)	15.38 (15.73)	10.76

Table 2. The IR frequencies (cm⁻¹) of interest with tentative assignments

Comps	C-H and N-H stretches	C=N stretches	SO ₂ -N < Band I and II
5	3265s 3055w 2972w	1588s	1177s 1397m
6	3510s 3437s 3188w	1614s	1125s 1321m
7	3499s 3423s 3283s	1602s	1130s 1365s
8	3273s 2938w 2829s	1598s	1162s 1361s

6 H⁺ or 7 H⁺ or 8 H⁺, (c) 0.01 M HClO₄ + 0.03 M 5 H⁺ or 6 H⁺ or 7 H⁺ or 8 H⁺. The ligand perchlorates were obtained *in situ* by mixing quantitatively 5/6/7/8 and HClO₄ in appropriate molar ratio. The aggressive environment used was 0.6 M aqueous NaCl solution prepared from AR grade reagent and double distilled water. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 6.0. Oxygen content of the sodium chloride solution was 7.3 mg/L. All other reagents were of AR quality. THERMO-NORHAN-USA Model SIX-NSS-200 was used to record EDS data.

Potentiodynamic polarization study

The potentiodynamic polarization studies were carried out with polished and degreased brass specimens having an exposed surface area of 0.25 cm². The electrochemical measurements were carried out in a standard three-electrode electrochemical cell of volume 100 ml. The counter electrode was a platinum plate with 1 cm² surface area, the reference electrode consisted of a commercial saturated calomel electrode with a Luggin capillary bridge and the working electrode was made up of brass. Polarization studies were carried out using potentiostat/galvanostat (ACM Instruments Gill AC) and the data obtained were analyzed using the software "ACM Instruments version 5" in air atmosphere. The degreased working electrode was immersed in 0.6 M aqueous NaCl solution and allowed to stabilize for 30 min²³. The cathodic and anodic polarization curves of brass specimen in the test solution with and without inhibitors were recorded at a scan rate of 1 mV/s in 0.6 M aqueous NaCl solution (pH 6) at 30 ± 0.5 °C. The inhibition efficiencies of the compounds were determined from corrosion current density using the Tafel extrapolation method.

Electrochemical AC impedance studies

AC impedance measurements were conducted at room

temperature using "ACM Instruments Gill AC". The instruments were controlled by the software "ACM Instruments version 5" between 1 mHz and 100 kHz. An AC sinusoid of $\sim \pm 10$ mV was applied at corrosion potential (E_{corr}). The brass sample with an exposing surface area of 0.25 cm^2 was used as the working electrode. A three electrode electrochemical cell of volume 100 ml with a platinum plate electrode and a saturated calomel electrode was used²⁴.

Results and discussion

The ability of an organic molecule to inhibit metal corrosion depends on several factors and some of them are the shape, aromaticity and/or conjugation, bonding strength to metal surface, the presence of heteroatom and the type and number of bonding atoms or groups²⁵⁻²⁷. The inhibition efficiency of **1** is 55.6%. It is increased by 11.6% after introducing the $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-SO}_2$ group (**3**), due to (a) higher molecular size, (b) π -electron contribution of the benzene ring and (c) presence of more active adsorption sites²⁸. The -COOH group of **3** is converted to imidazoline group and the resultant compound **5** is highly basic. The inhibition efficiency of **5** is found to be 76.9%.

The increased inhibition efficiency is due to the presence of more active adsorption sites containing nitrogen. The corresponding tetrahydropyrimidine derivative (**7**) exhibits higher inhibition efficiency (90.2%) due to larger size of the molecule.

The inhibition efficiencies²⁹ of **9** and **10** are less than **5** and **7** respectively.

9 (I.E. = 68.1)

10 (I.E. = 80.5)

It is observed that **5** is less basic than **9** due to presence of benzene ring. In spite of low basic character the inhibition efficiency of **5** is greater than **9**. This increased efficiency is due to the effect of π -electron of the benzene ring resulting better adsorption. Similar trend is also observed in case of compounds **7** and **10**. Inhibition efficiencies of *p*-aminobenzoic acid and its derivatives follow similar trend. *para* Compounds are found to be better inhibitors than *ortho* compounds due to better surface coverage. The inhibition efficiency of these compounds increases in the order : **1** < **3** < **2** < **5** < **4** < **6** < **7** < **8**.

Potentiodynamic polarization study :

The cathodic and anodic polarization curves of brass in 0.6 M aqueous NaCl solution with varying concentrations of **1** to **10** are shown in the Figs. 2-11. The potentiodynamic polarization parameters are listed in Table 2. Inhibition efficiencies³⁰ are calculated using the following equation,

$$\text{Inhibition Efficiency} = \left[\frac{I_{\text{corr}} - I_{\text{corr(inh)}}}{I_{\text{corr}}} \right] \times 100$$

where $I_{\text{corr(inh)}}$ and I_{corr} are the corrosion current density value with and without inhibitor, respectively.

Fig. 2. Effect of 1 on the polarization curve of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution at 1 mV/s.

Fig. 5. Effect of 4 on the polarization curve of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution at 1 mV/s.

Fig. 3. Effect of 2 on the polarization curve of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution at 1 mV/s.

Fig. 6. Effect of 5 on the polarization curve of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution at 1 mV/s.

Fig. 4. Effect of 3 on the polarization curve of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution at 1 mV/s.

Fig. 7. Effect of 6 on the polarization curve of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution at 1 mV/s.

Fig. 8. Effect of 7 on the polarization curve of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution at 1 mV/s.

Fig. 11. Effect of 10 on the polarization curve of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution at 1 mV/s.

Fig. 9. Effect of 8 on the polarization curve of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution at 1 mV/s.

Fig. 10. Effect of 9 on the polarization curve of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution at 1 mV/s.

From Table 3, it is observed that the E_{corr} values are shifted towards positive direction in the presence of inhibitors. Corrosion current density also decreases in presence of these inhibitors. The cathodic and anodic curves are shifted towards the more positive potential region in presence of inhibitors which indicate that addition of these derivatives reduces anodic dissolution and decrease the rate of oxygen reduction by retarding the transfer of O_2 to the cathodic sites of the brass surface. Hence these derivatives are mixed type inhibitors.

Table 3. The electrochemical parameters and inhibition efficiency values for the corrosion of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution

Inhibitors	Concentration (M)	E_{corr} (mV) vs SCE	I_{corr} ($\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$)	I.E. (%)
	0	-301.8	6.14	
1	4×10^{-4}	-268.5	3.88	36.8
	4×10^{-5}	-243.4	2.90	52.7
	4×10^{-6}	-261.3	3.47	43.4
2	4×10^{-4}	-241.6	1.99	67.5
	4×10^{-5}	-257.5	1.74	71.6
	4×10^{-6}	-245.0	2.01	43.4
3	4×10^{-4}	-257.8	2.26	63.1
	4×10^{-5}	-238.7	2.15	64.9
	4×10^{-6}	-251.7	3.12	49.1
4	4×10^{-4}	-250.6	1.46	76.2
	4×10^{-5}	-243.0	1.22	80.1
	4×10^{-6}	-248.6	1.45	76.3
5	4×10^{-4}	-238.4	2.15	64.9
	4×10^{-5}	-251.8	1.58	74.1
	4×10^{-6}	-231.0	1.69	72.4

Table-3 (contd.)

6	4×10^{-4}	-253.3	1.40	77.1
	4×10^{-5}	-251.0	0.74	87.9
	4×10^{-6}	-221.9	1.29	72.4
7	4×10^{-4}	-267.7	0.86	85.9
	4×10^{-5}	-240.7	0.73	88.1
	4×10^{-6}	-268.1	0.82	86.6
8	4×10^{-4}	-239.2	0.71	88.4
	4×10^{-5}	-201.5	0.35	94.2
	4×10^{-6}	-212.5	0.52	91.5
9	4×10^{-4}	-263.0	2.56	58.3
	4×10^{-5}	-246.2	2.15	65.7
	4×10^{-6}	-228.9	2.26	63.1
10	4×10^{-4}	-244.6	1.44	76.5
	4×10^{-5}	-226.1	1.33	78.3
	4×10^{-6}	-227.1	1.43	76.7

Fig. 14. Effect of 3 on the impedance behaviour of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution.

Electrochemical AC impedance studies :

The effects of 1 to 10 on the impedance behaviour of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution are given in Figs. 12-21. These curves show Nyquist plots of brass in presence of

Fig. 12. Effect of 1 on the impedance behaviour of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution.

Fig. 15. Effect of 4 on the impedance behaviour of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution.

Fig. 13. Effect of 2 on the impedance behaviour of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution.

Fig. 16. Effect of 5 on the impedance behaviour of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution.

Fig. 17. Effect of 6 on the impedance behaviour of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution.

Fig. 18. Effect of 7 on the impedance behaviour of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution.

Fig. 19. Effect of 8 on the impedance behaviour of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution.

Fig. 20. Effect of 9 on the impedance behaviour of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution.

Fig. 21. Effect of 10 on the impedance behaviour of brass in 0.6 M NaCl solution.

inhibitors and in absence of inhibitors. These plots reveal that the impedance response of the brass has significantly changed after using these inhibitors. Various impedance parameters such as charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}), double layer capacitance (C_{dl}) and inhibition efficiency (IE) are given in Table 3. The charge transfer values are calculated from the difference in impedance at lower and higher frequencies as suggested by Haruyama *et al.*³¹. The percentage efficiency of corrosion of brass is calculated by R_{ct} as follows³² :

$$IE = [R_{ct}^{-1} - R_{ct\text{ inh}}^{-1} / R_{ct}^{-1}] \times 100$$

where $R_{ct\text{ inh}}$ and R_{ct} are charge transfer resistance values with and without inhibitor respectively. The trend of increase in inhibition efficiency is same as in polarization study i.e. there is a good agreement between the results obtained from polarization and impedance studies. The result (Table 4) shows that the C_{dl} value decreases when inhibitors are used. This decrease in the C_{dl} may result from a decrease in local dielectric constant and/or an

Table 4. The impedance measurements and inhibition efficiency values of sulphonamido derivatives for the corrosion of brass in 0.6 M NaCl

Inhibitors	Concentration (M)	R_{ct} (K ohm)	C_{dl} (F)	I.E. (R_{ct}) (%)
	0	0.358	2.38×10^{-4}	
1	4×10^{-4}	0.595	5.33×10^{-5}	39.8
	4×10^{-5}	0.808	2.61×10^{-4}	58.5
	4×10^{-6}	0.677	2.53×10^{-5}	47.7
2	4×10^{-4}	1.129	7.22×10^{-5}	68.1
	4×10^{-5}	1.488	1.61×10^{-4}	75.9
	4×10^{-6}	1.222	1.62×10^{-5}	70.7
3	4×10^{-4}	1.012	7.08×10^{-5}	64.9
	4×10^{-5}	1.176	2.25×10^{-4}	69.5
	4×10^{-6}	0.777	7.08×10^{-5}	53.9

Table-4 (contd.)

4	4×10^{-4}	1.759	1.51×10^{-4}	79.6
	4×10^{-5}	2.339	1.61×10^{-4}	84.6
	4×10^{-6}	1.472	1.63×10^{-4}	75.6
5	4×10^{-4}	1.212	1.55×10^{-4}	70.4
	4×10^{-5}	1.767	4.17×10^{-5}	79.6
	4×10^{-6}	1.452	5.63×10^{-5}	75.0
6	4×10^{-4}	1.781	3.64×10^{-5}	79.8
	4×10^{-5}	3.621	1.48×10^{-4}	90.1
	4×10^{-6}	2.061	1.55×10^{-4}	82.6
7	4×10^{-4}	3.897	5.53×10^{-5}	90.8
	4×10^{-5}	4.710	8.18×10^{-5}	92.3
	4×10^{-6}	3.640	2.50×10^{-5}	90.1
8	4×10^{-4}	3.921	6.12×10^{-5}	90.8
	4×10^{-5}	10.35	4.80×10^{-5}	96.5
	4×10^{-6}	7.250	1.33×10^{-4}	95.0
9	4×10^{-4}	0.985	9.89×10^{-5}	63.6
	4×10^{-5}	1.214	2.38×10^{-4}	70.5
	4×10^{-6}	1.121	7.26×10^{-5}	68.0
10	4×10^{-4}	1.800	1.88×10^{-4}	80.1
	4×10^{-5}	2.073	5.19×10^{-5}	82.7
	4×10^{-6}	1.860	1.58×10^{-4}	80.7

increase in the thickness of electrical double layer. This fact suggests the adsorption of the molecule on the alloy surface and its dissolution is reduced³³.

Conclusion :

(i) All investigated compounds have shown inhibiting properties for brass in 0.6 M aqueous sodium chloride solution.

(ii) The corrosion inhibition efficiency of the compounds increases in the following order : $1 < 3 < 2 < 5 < 4 < 6 < 7 < 8$.

(iii) Significant improvement in the inhibition property of amino benzoic acids is observed by introducing $C_6H_5SO_2$ group.

(iv) Inhibition efficiency is further improved when the carboxyl group is converted to imidazoline or 1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidine group.

(v) The *para* compounds are found to be better inhibitor than the corresponding *ortho* compounds due to better surface coverage.

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